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Two new species of the genus *Phaea* Newman, 1840 (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) from Central and South America

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Rostov Branch of the All-Russian Plant Quarantine Center, 20th line, 43/16, Rostov-on-Don 344037 Russia. E-mail: dorcadion@yandex.ru

Abstract. Two new cerambycid species of the genus *Phaea* Newman, 1840 are described. *Phaea hirsuticollis* sp. n. from Costa Rica is similar to *Ph. monostigma* (Haldeman, 1847) and *Ph. hoegei* Bates, 1881 and differs from both species in the coloration of body, pronotal sculpture, two large hair brush on pronotal umbone. *Phaea mehli* sp. n. from Ecuador is similar to *Ph. kaitlinae* Chemsak, 1999 and *Ph. rufiventris* Bates, 1872 and differs from the first species in the shape of umbone, pronotal coloration, sculpture of head and pronotum; it differs from *Ph. rufiventris* by coloration of scutellum and antennae, pubescence, shape of umbone.

Key words: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Lamiinae, *Phaea*, new species, Costa Rica, Ecuador.

Два новых вида жуков-усачей рода *Phaea* Newman, 1840 (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) из Центральной и Южной Америки

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Ростовский филиал ФГБУ «ВНИИКР», 20-я линия, 43/16, Ростов-на-Дону 344037 Россия. E-mail: dorcadion@yandex.ru

Резюме. При обработке коллекции Cerambycidae Датского музея естественной истории были обнаружены экземпляры двух новых видов рода *Phaea* Newman, 1840, описание которых приведено в статье. Первый новый вид, *Ph. hirsuticollis* sp. n., относительно близок к *Ph. monostigma* (Haldeman, 1847) и *Ph. hoegei* Bates, 1881 и отличается окраской тела, скульптурой переднеспинки, наличием двух крупных волосяных щеток на переднегрудной мозоли. Известен только из Коста-Рики. Второй новый вид, *Ph. mehli* sp. n., происходящий из Эквадора, близок к *Ph. kaitlinae* Chemsak, 1999 и *Ph. rufiventris* Bates, 1872, но отличается формой переднегрудной мозоли, характером скульптуры головы и опушения антенн.

Ключевые слова: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Lamiinae, *Phaea*, новые виды, Коста-Рика, Эквадор.

Twenty species of *Phaea* Newman, 1840 are known from Costa Rica [Bezark, 2019] and only one from Ecuador [Bezark, Monne, 2013; Bezark, 2019]. Two new species were discovered in the collection of the Natural History Museum of Denmark (NMHD) and are described herein.

Phaea hirsuticollis sp. n. (Figs 1–4)

Material. Holotype, ♀ (NMHD): “Costa Rica, Ørsted”, “*Phaea* sp. M.A. Monne det., 1992”.

Description. Body length 11 mm. Elytra, scutellum, abdomen, legs, meta- and mesothorax dark brown; head and pronotum orange, with small black spot, laterally, on each side; antennomeres dark brown, apically black, with slightly visible light annulation at base (Fig. 1). Head large, wider than pronotum, coarsely and sparsely punctated, covered with sparse yellow recumbent hairs and moderately dense erect black setae; genae slightly longer than lower lobe of eye. Antennae reaching elytral apical third, covered with thin dark hairs and erect long black hairs; pedicel elongate, 1.3 times as long as width; antennomere 3 equal to 4 and slightly longer than 5. Scape with rugose sculpture in apical half (Fig. 4).

Pronotum square, with glabrous shining umbone on disc and with a pair of small lateral tubercles. Umbone slightly elevated, ovoid, indistinctly delimited, base of pronotum constricted but with not deeply. Pronotal punctation very sparse; umbone with two lateral areas of large dense punctures, each with dense brush

of distinct erect hair (Fig. 2). Pronotum covered with fine yellow recumbent and sporadic long erect black setae, in middle basal constriction forming a sparse tuft.

Scutellum transverse, tetragonal. Elytra elongate, widest after middle, with widely rounded apices, almost truncate. Elytral punctation coarse and dense, but punctures distinctly separated, irregular; surface with distinct microsculpture between punctures. Elytral pubescence consisting of very thin (sculpture not hidden), dark brown, recumbent hairs; surface of elytra additionally with long black erect hairs (Fig. 3), more dense around scutellum.

Ventral side shiny, very sparsely punctured, with mixed light and dark erect setae.

Male is unknown.

Differential diagnosis. This new species is similar to *Phaea monostigma* (Haldeman, 1847) but differs by the presence of a pair black of hair brushes on the pronotal umbone, other antennal coloration and absence of two area of dense puncture on umbone. *Phaea hoegei* Bates 1881, distributed in Costa Rica has, unlike the new species, one black hair brush in the middle of the pronotal umbone and also differs by black marking on the umbone, black ventral side of body, legs and antennae. From other *Phaea* distributed in Costa Rica and neighboring countries, the new species clearly differs by the body coloration and the two hair brushes on the pronotal umbone.

Etymology. The name of this new species refers to its most evident character: a hair-brushed pronotum.

Figs 1–7. New species of the genus *Phaea*.

1–4 – *Ph. hirsuticollis* sp. n., female, holotype: 1 – dorsal view, 2 – lateral view, 3 – frontal view, 4 – head and antennomere 1; 5–7 – *Phaea mehli* sp. n., female, holotype: 5 – dorsal view, 6 – lateral view, 7 – head and pronotum.

Рис. 1–7. Новые виды рода *Phaea*.

1–4 – *Ph. hirsuticollis* sp. n., самка, голотип: 1 – вид сверху, 2 – вид сбоку, 3 – вид спереди, 4 – голова и антенномер 1; 5–7 – *Phaea mehli* sp. n., самка, голотип: 5 – вид сверху, 6 – вид сбоку, 7 – голова и переднеспинка.

Phaea mehli sp. n.
(Figs 5–7)

Material. Holotype, ♀ (NMHD): “Ecuador, Santorengo [probably San Lorenzo], la Recova, Dec. 1999; “*Phaea* ?sp. Ohle Mehl det., 2011”.

Description. Body length 8 mm. Elytra very dark brown; head and legs black; scutellum orange; meta- and mesoventrite red-orange, with dark brown coloration on epipleura and metaventrite, pronotum red, umbone and middle part of anterior margin black; abdomen reddish-orange with dark brown sides of ventrites, apical ventrite and pygidium completely dark brown, almost black; antennae black, except from antennomere 7 light orange-brown (Fig. 5).

Head not large, coarsely and very sparsely punctate, covered with sparse light recumbent hairs and sparse erect light longer hairs; genae distinctly shorter than lower lobe of eye. Antennae reaching apical fourth of elytra, densely covered with thin light hairs and erect long brown hairs; pedicel elongate, 1.6 times as long as wide; antennomere 3 equal to 4 and distinctly longer than 5. Scape with coarse and relatively sparse punctures.

Pronotum square; pronotal umbone square, convex, with sides distinctly delimited; basal impression wide, apically narrow. Pronotal punctation very sparse; umbone with coarse but not dense punctures (Fig. 6). Pronotum sparsely covered with thin erect light hairs.

Scutellum tetragonal; elytra elongate, widest after middle, with widely rounded apices. Elytral punctation very coarse, moderately dense, punctures distinctly separated, forming rows in basal half, irregular in apical half. Elytral pubescence consisting of thin (sculpture not hidden), light, recumbent hairs; surface of elytra additionally with sparse long light erect hairs, more dense around scutellum (Fig. 7).

Ventral side very sparsely punctured, with light pubescence.

Male is unknown.

Differential diagnosis. This new species is very similar to *Phaea kaitlinae* Chemsak 1999 and *Ph. rufiventris* Bates,

1872. Both species are only known from Mexico. *Phaea andrewsi* Chemsak 1999, the only other species known from Ecuador, is not similar to this new species, has orange legs, antennae, head, pronotum, basal third of elytra and ventral side of body. The new species differs from *Ph. kaitlinae* in the coloration of pronotum and antennae (presence of dark anterior pronotal margin, antennomeres 8–11 light-colored), shape of pronotal umbone (square, not ovoid), main pubescence of antennae light, sparse punctures on head. *Phaea rufiventris* differs from *Ph. mehli* sp. n. by the longitudinal umbone with very sparse punctures, not annulate antennomeres, black scutellum.

Etymology. The new species is named in memory of Mr Ole Mehl.

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References

- Bezark L.G. 2019. A photographic catalog of the Cerambycidae of the World. New World Cerambycidae Catalog. Available at: <http://bezbycids.com/byciddb/wdefault.asp?w=n> (accessed 21 January 2020).
- Bezark L.G., Monne M.A. 2013. Checklist of the Oxypeltidae, Vesperidae, Disteniidae and Cerambycidae, (Coleoptera) of the Western Hemisphere. Rancho Dominguez: BioQuip Publications. 484 p.

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